

Study of the Exponential Growth of Bacteria: Using the concepts of Numerical Calculation in Scilab

Eduarda Akemi Sato Sierra, Dr. Alexandre Maniçoba de Oliveira.

Instituto Federal de Educação, Ciência e Tecnologia de São Paulo (IFSP) Campus Cubatão
akemi.s@aluno.ifsp.edu.br, amanicoba@ifsp.edu.br.

Summary – In this article, the exponential growth of bacteria was studied, using the concepts of Numerical Calculation together with the Scilab language to assist this project. A demonstrative growth rate was analyzed and through the use of the code it is possible to obtain a graph, helping to observe the behavior of the bacteria.

Keywords: Numerical Calculation, bacterial population growth, Scilab.

INTRODUCTION

Food waste due to the action of microorganisms is a major social and economic problem around the world. According to the FDA (Food and Drug Administration), probably 20% of food is wasted due to expiration dates, which costs the USA around US\$161 billion per year [3]. The shelf life of all products must be respected, after all, it is defined by the time in which the product is safe for consumption. Qualities such as color, flavor, texture, odor and compliance with the nutritional declaration can be deteriorated by microbial species [2].

The expiration date of food is directly related to the microbiological quality of the food, being influenced primarily by the type of microorganisms present and their initial quantity, subsequently by the multiplication of these bacteria in the food [5]. The behavior of these species is influenced by the attributes of this food and storage. Another major deterioration factor is temperature, in a warmer and more humid environment there is a greater proliferation of bacteria and fungi.

When it comes to food poisoning, bacteria lead the ranking of occurrences with 95% of cases and are responsible for 70% of outbreaks, according to the Center for Disease Control in the USA [3]. The proliferation of these microorganisms in food is often due to inadequate handling of these products, either due to hygienic habits or illnesses of the handlers [4].

Bacteria reproduce asexually, most of them by binary division. In this reproduction, the bacterial genetic material duplicates itself in the cytoplasm and causes cell division, thus, one bacterium generates another bacterium, doubling the original quantity. The bacterial growth process is exponential and if control is not carried out, it will generate large population growth [2].

Figure 1 shows the binary division process of bacteria.

Figure 1- Binary Fission Source: CTISM

Biology and mathematics have a relationship of mutual contribution, it is possible to describe natural phenomena through mathematics. Biomathematics is the area that uses mathematical models to study the behavior of biological systems. In Malthusian Theory, Malthus concludes that the population follows a geometric progression, that is, when the growth factor is greater than 1, growth is exponential [1]. To calculate this growth rate, the equation is used:

$$\frac{dN}{dT} = rN$$

Where N is the population size, T is the time and r is the per capita value of growth rate.

Among the mathematical models there are primary models that describe growth in relation to time and secondary models that, in addition to the time factor, analyze one or more environmental factors [5]. Factors such as temperature, pH and gas composition of the atmosphere do not normally remain constant, which makes modeling the behavior of these microorganisms subject to small variations [4].

A simulation was carried out by ECA (Control and Automation Engineering) students at the IFSP Cubatão campus, where the Scilab 5.5 tool was used. To simulate the population growth of bacteria by the time factor, according to a primary mathematical model. Table 1 below shows the number of initial bacteria and the analyzed doubling time:

NUMBER OF BACTERIA	TIME (hours)
100	0
200	6
400	12
6400	36
25.600	48

Table 1 – merely fanciful values for system analysis Source: Author (2023)

To simulate this growth on an exponential graph, the following code was used:

```
X = [0; 6; 12; 36; 48];  
N = length(x);  
Y = [100; 200; 400; 6400; 25600];  
// We create a vector x with points in time, n is the number of elements in x,  
// ey is the vector containing the corresponding bacterial population.  
A = [x x.^0];  
// We create a matrix A with two columns, where the first column is
```

DEVELOPMENT

```
equal to x
// and the second column is x raised to
the zero power, that is, 1.
Th = inv(A'*A) * A' * log(y);
// We calculate th, which are the linear
regression coefficients. We use the
formula
// linear regression to fit a
logarithmic curve to data y and matrix A.
Ya = A*th;
// We calculate ya, which is the
bacterial population estimated by the
coefficient th found.
a = 0.1155245;
b = 4.6051702;
b2 = exp(b);
// We determine the values of a, b and
b2 that will be used later in the
exponential equation.
JT = linspace(0, 72, 100);
// We create a vector t containing 100
equidistant points from 0 to 72 hours.
For i = 1:100
Function(i) = b2 * exp(a * t(i));
END
// A loop was used to calculate the
function, which is the estimated number of
bacteria over time
// we determine the exponential equation
with values a, b2 and t.
Figure(1)
Plot(x, y, '.')
Plot(t, function, 'b')
Xlabel('Time (hours)')
Ylabel('Bacteria Population')
Title('Bacteria Population Growth')
// The first graph was created by
plotting the 'x' and 'y' points and
defining an approximate growth curve.
Axis labels and a title were also added.
```

The exponential graph, for the most part, is made by adjusting a mathematical model by inserting different data obtained. In the case of this experiment, the code of a scientific initiation (Thomes et al, 2017) was studied to create the graph [6].

Graph 1 – population growth of bacteria Source: Author (2023)

With the help of this code, it was possible to obtain graph 1, showing and proving that the growth rate of bacteria has exponential behavior. Although the graph is showing continuous growth, it is important to point out that eventually the resources favorable for this growth run out, causing a slowdown and logistical behavior.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Through this study it was possible to acquire

practical and theoretical knowledge about the growth of bacteria. Along with the knowledge, it is also possible to visualize the importance of Number Calculation in the training of future engineers, considering that engineers need to solve problems. By executing the code proposed for this article and correcting the errors involved, the understanding of how the Scilab programming language works will provide better development in other articles.

Also studying bacteria and their behavior, the importance of studying the growth rate of these microorganisms is clear, given the harm they cause to health, as for the Economy. By modeling this growth, it is possible to analyze the best way to apply control over it, avoiding the degradation of part of the food.

The application of this method proved to be efficient in describing the reproduction of bacteria and obtained satisfactory results. Although the code complies with what is proposed and contributes to the analysis of microbial growth, it is also important to analyze other factors that alter time variation (such as temperature, atmospheric gases, presence of inhibitors, among others).

Therefore, it is possible to conclude that for a better analysis of this growth, it is necessary to deepen the area, making it possible to move from a primary model to a secondary model, where factors other than time are analyzed. Using a secondary mathematical model, the results obtained will come closer and closer to the real value, contributing to better control.

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